

Formate Dehydrogenase: Recent Developments for NADH and NADPH Recycling in Biocatalysis

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Formate dehydrogenases (FDHs) catalyze the oxidation of formate to CO₂ while reducing NAD(P)⁺ to NAD(P)H and are classified into two main classes: metal-dependent (Mo- or W-containing) and metal-independent FDHs. The latter are oxygen-tolerant and relevant as a cofactor regeneration system for various bioprocesses and gained more and more attention due to their ability to catalyze the reverse CO₂ reduction. This review

gives an overview of metal-independent FDHs, the recent advances made in this field, and their relevance for future applications in biocatalysis. This includes the exploitation of novel FDHs which have altered co-substrate specificity as well as enzyme engineering approaches to improve process stability and general performance.

1. Introduction

Biocatalysis developed in the last decades into a full-fledged technology with involvement in various processes, some reaching industrial scale, such as production of duloxetine, boceprevir and sitagliptin to name a few.^[1] This progression is the merit of the advances of DNA synthesis and sequencing and enzyme engineering methods, including rational design and directed evolution.^[2,3] Further improvement was achieved by reducing the library size and simplifying of the screening processes, making these methods standard practice in most laboratories.^[3] With the recent bioinformatic milestones involving AI-based structure predictions *via* AlphaFold, growing databases and accessibility to a plethora of various tools for enzyme engineering, even further development of the biocatalytic sector is to be expected.^[4] However, several limitations remain to be addressed. One of the main concerns is the reliance on costly cofactors such as NADH and NADPH as many reactions of interest involve oxidoreductases that require the respective electron donor.^[5] In nature, reduced nicotinamides such as NADH and NADPH are a powerful and ubiquitous source of electrons. These are redox active cosubstrates or cofactors for numerous oxidoreductases and balance the energy cycle in the cellular context. In biocatalysis, these can be used as in the living matter considering two major aspects-stability under process conditions and recycling after electrons have been provided for other reactions. The latter is until now a subject of research and development. Recycling of NADH and NADPH can be done by enzymatic, chemical, electrochemical, and photochemical methods. Among those methods, the enzymatic alternatives often are considered to be greener and present certain advantages such as low environmental impact, 100% selectivity, and high total turnover numbers.^[6] So far, enzymatic regeneration is mostly achieved using formate dehydrogenases (FDHs), glucose dehydrogenases (GDHs), alcohol dehydrogenases (ADHs) and phosphite dehydrogenases (PDHs), of which each has its own limitations (Scheme 1). For instance, GDHs require additional pH control due to formation of gluconic acid and PDHs display a restricted range of optimal pH and temperature.^[7] ADHs are reported to be temperature sensitive

and might be problematic in reactions involving ketones due to the reversibility of the alcohol oxidation.^[8] This makes the formate dehydrogenases a promising candidate for cofactor regeneration.

2. The Formate Dehydrogenases

FDHs catalyze the oxidation of formate to CO₂ while reducing NAD(P)⁺ to NAD(P)H by direct hydride transfer. Reduction of CO₂ can also be carried out by FDHs, though the formate oxidation is heavily favored due to the redox potential of the enzymatic CO₂ reduction towards formate of about -420 mV.^[9] Two main classes of formate dehydrogenases can be distinguished: metal-dependent (Mo- or W-containing) FDHs (EC1.17.1.9) and metal-independent oxygen-tolerant FDHs (EC 1.17.1.9 and EC.1.17.1.10). Both classes also exhibit distinct structural features (Figure 1).

Scheme 1. Enzymatic NADH and NADPH recycling systems.

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Figure 1. Structural view of the two FDH families. (A) metal-dependent FDHs from *Methylobacterium extorquens* AM1 (PDB: 8 J83) and *Escherichia coli* (PDB: 1QKF) with the respective subunits color coded. (B) Homodimeric metal-independent FDHs from *Granulicella mallensis* (PDB: 4XYB), *Candida boidinii* (PDB: 5DN9) and *Physcomitrium patens* (PDB: 7ARZ) with mitochondrial origin. Structures were depicted using PyMol.^[10]

Metal-dependent FDHs contain Mo or W in the active site coordinated by cysteine (or selenocysteine), metal binding pterin guanine dinucleotide cofactor (MGD) and a small ligand oxygen or sulfur species.^[11] Additionally, depending on the involved subunits, various other cofactors such as [2Fe-2S] and [4Fe-4S] clusters, FMN, FAD or heme can be utilized and as

well as a variety of electron acceptors comprising of NAD⁺, cytochromes, ferredoxins, quinones and coenzyme F₄₂₀. This makes the metal-dependent FDHs a rather broad enzyme class, which was intensively discussed in previous reviews.^[11,12] Despite offering rather high activity compared to the metal-independent FDHs, metal-dependent FDHs suffer from oxygen

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sensitivity and therefore require strictly anaerobic conditions, which are on the one hand more difficult to control and are also not compatible with oxygen-dependent reactions.^[13] Moreover, the need for multiple cofactors further increase protein production hurdles. Thus, metal-independent and oxygen-tolerant FDHs represent an interesting and significant alternative as a biocatalyst.

Oxygen-tolerant formate dehydrogenases mediate direct hydride transfer from formate to NAD(P)⁺ without assistance of metal ions or other cofactors.^[14,15] In the microbial host organisms, FDHs are presumed to be primarily involved in detoxification of formate, which is formed during the C1 metabolism by methanol dehydrogenase and formaldehyde dehydrogenase. However, it is also hypothesized that FDHs can participate in metabolization of oxalic acid as proposed for the white-rot fungus *Ceriporiopsis subvermispora*.^[16] Despite yielding NADH, FDHs are considered to be primarily important for the detoxification process. In plants, FDHs are hypothesized to play an important role in stress response and ROS-mediated signal-

ing between mitochondria and chloroplast as reported for *Nicotiana benthamiana* and *Arabidopsis thaliana*.^[17] Over the last decades, various FDHs were reported, of which most are only active towards NAD⁺ (Table 1).

The reported FDHs can be classified according to their sequence based on multiple sequence alignment. For a more robust phylogenetic tree, uncharacterized putative FDHs were added (Figure 2). Figure 2 demonstrates that plant and most bacterial FDHs form compact groups, except for *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* FDHs which are more distant to the other bacterial FDHs. Fungal FDHs show more variety compared to the plant and bacterial ones. Overall, NADP⁺-accepting FDHs are also forming a group consisting of *Burkholderia dolosa* PC543, *Burkholderia stabilis* and *Granulicella mallensis*. The remaining NADP⁺-accepting FDH from *Lactobacillus buchneri* is more distant to this group, indicating that the NADP⁺-acceptance might have coevolved. The uncharacterized putative FDH from *Lentilactobacillus diolivorans*, giving its relation to FDH from

Table 1. Reported FDH representatives with their respective cosubstrate acceptance.

Abbreviation	Accession number	Activity with NAD ⁺	Activity with NADP ⁺	Organism	Ref.
CboFDH	CAB54834	yes	no	<i>Candida boidinii</i>	[14]
CmFDH	CAA57036	yes	no	<i>Candida methyllica</i>	[18]
KpFDH	CAY70992	yes	no	<i>Komagataella phaffii</i>	[19]
OpFDH	XP_013932954	yes	no	<i>Ogataea parapolymorpha</i>	[20]
ScFDH	NP_015033	yes	no	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	[20]
CdFDH	XP_002420645	yes	no	<i>Candida dubliniensis</i>	[21]
GsFDH	BAF98206	yes	no	<i>Gelatoporia subvermispora</i>	[16]
TcFDH	XP_006697051	yes	no	<i>Thermochaetoides thermophila</i> DSM 1495	[22]
TmFDH	XP_003662055	yes	no	<i>Thermothelomyces thermophilus</i>	[23]
PhyFDH	XP_024399650	yes	no	<i>Physcomitrella patens</i>	[20]
GmFDH	QYU73840	yes	no	<i>Glycine max</i>	[20]
CaFDH	AGE13354	yes	no	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	[24]
GhFDH	XP_016746875.2	yes	no	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	[25]
AtFDH	NP_001330045	yes	no	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	[17]
LbFDH	AEB72361	yes	yes	<i>Lactobacillus buchneri</i>	[26]
BdFDH	ETP61471	yes	yes	<i>Burkholderia dolosa</i> PC543	[27]
BstFDH	ACF35003	yes	yes	<i>Burkholderia stabilis</i>	[28]
GraFDH2	WP_014265374	yes	yes	<i>Granulicella mallensis</i>	[15]
GraFDH1	WP_014264099	yes	no	<i>Granulicella mallensis</i>	[29]
AspFDH	WP_098736599	yes	no	<i>Azospirillum palustre</i>	[30]
MoFDH	CAA73696	yes	no	<i>Moraxella</i> sp.	[31]
PcFDH	BAB64941	yes	no	<i>Paracoccus</i> sp. 12-A	[32]
TbFDH	BAC92737	yes	no	<i>Thiobacillus</i> sp. KNK65MA	[33]
AbaFDH	BAC65346	yes	no	<i>Ancylobacter aquaticus</i> KNK607 M	[34]
PsFDH	P33160.3	yes	no	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. 101	[35]
MycFDH	BAB69476	yes	no	<i>Mycobacterium vaccae</i>	[36]
XaFDH	WP_029558741	yes	no	<i>Xanthobacter</i> sp. 91	[37]
AbnFDH	WP_013168047	yes	no	<i>Ancylobacter novellus</i>	[38]
BsFDH	WP_061140900	yes	no	<i>Bacillus simplex</i>	[39]
SaFDH	YP_498741	yes	no	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	[20]

Figure 2. Minimum evolution tree of reported FDHs. The sequences were retrieved from NCBI database and the distance tree was generated with MEGA X employing the pre-set parameters for minimum evolution tree computation. Numbers at nodes indicate the percentage of bootstrap support based on 1000 bootstrap replicates. Bootstrap values below 50 are not shown. Representatives reported to naturally accept NADP⁺ are highlighted in the red box. Biochemically characterized FDHs are highlighted by asterisk (*).

Lactobacillus buchneri, might be naturally accepting NADP⁺ as well. FDHs are a highly conserved enzyme class.

3. Structural Insights

In the last decades, many structural investigations were conducted on FDHs and various representatives were crystallized and their structures solved.^[15,21,22,40] So far, all of those FDHs are found to be homodimers, of which each monomer consists of two Rossmann-fold domains: the catalytic domain and the cofactor binding domain. As for *Cbo*FDH, the cofactor binding domain is formed by the middle part of the primary structure (residues N119 to S313) whereas the catalytic domain comprises of the remaining N- and C-terminal residues (Figure 3).^[40,41]

Further structural analysis of FDH from *Candida boidinii* suggests that upon substrate binding, the catalytic domain is tilted inwards by 14° and thus, closing the active site and changing the conformation from apo- to the holo-form. These conformations are also referred to as the open and closed conformation (Figure 4A).^[42] Interestingly, structural analysis of the NAD⁺-dependent FDH from *Thiobacillus* sp. KNK65MA and naturally NADP⁺-accepting FDH from *Granulicella mallensis* showed that cosubstrate binding was sufficient to induce transition into the closed form, despite the lack of a formate tunnel, possibly indicating why the K_M values for formate are always in the range of 4–6 mM among all reported FDHs.^[15,43] In contrary, formate binding does not seem to induce conformation change as crystallization of *Ps*FDH with only formate resembled mostly the closed conformation and, so far, no other structures with only formate in the active site were reported.^[44] Despite being a highly conserved enzyme class, FDHs show also structural features, differing between bacterial, fungal and plant origin. For instance, bacterial FDHs have an extended loop of approx. 30 amino acids that is located after the α 1 helix of the catalytic domain, which is not present in fungal and plant FDHs (Figure 4B–D). The only exceptions among the reported FDHs represent *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus simplex* FDHs, which are rather distantly related to the loop-bearing represen-

Figure 3. Domain organization of FDHs. Exemplary alignment of *Cbo*FDH and *Gra*FDH with coloring indicating the structural organization of the primary sequence segments. Alignment was depicted using ESPrpt.^[47] Structures were depicted using PyMol.^[10]

Figure 4. Structural features of FDHs. (A) Conformational change of *CboFDH* from apo-form (yellow, PDB: 5DNA) to holo-form (green, PDB: 5DN9). Loop region located after the $\alpha 1$ helix (purple) and N-terminal extension (red) of (B) *CboFDH*, (C) *GraFDH* and (D) *PhyFDH*. Structures were depicted using PyMol.^[10]

tatives. The role of this loop remains to be elucidated. Furthermore, plant FDHs possess an extended N-terminus, forming a signal peptide.^[45] This signal peptide is likely essential for translocation from cytoplasm into mitochondria or chloroplasts, where it is subsequently cleaved off.^[45,46] Some FDHs originating from fungi such as *Ajellomyces capsulatus* and *Aspergillus oryzae* among others, are hypothesized to contain similar signal peptide structure based on sequence alignments, suggesting the existence of comparable transport systems.^[45] However, biochemical and structural characterizations of these representatives are still pending.

Initially it was assumed that FDHs are strictly accepting only NAD^+ as cosubstrate. However, naturally NADP^+ -accepting FDHs were recently discovered in *Granulicella mallensis*, *Burkholderia stabilis*, *Burkholderia dolosa* PC543 and *Lactobacillus buchneri*. For the *Granulicella mallensis* FDH (*GraFDH2*), the crystal structure was solved and allowed a more detailed view on the cofactor specificity.^[15]

In examining the loop regions responsible for cofactor specificity of *GraFDH* and *PsFDH*, *GraFDH* features Ala at position 222, whereas *PsFDH* has Asp at the corresponding position 221 (Figure 5A and B). This single substitution has a dual impact: it removes the acidic properties that would repel the phosphate group of NADP^+ and creates more space to accommodate it. Moreover, the loop in *GraFDH* shifts towards the solvent, opening additional room for the phosphate group.

Figure 5. (A) Binding site of ribose moiety of NAD^+ in *PsFDH* (PDB: 2NAD). (B) Binding site of the ribose phosphate moiety of NADP^+ in *GraFDH2* (PDB: 4XYB). (C) Binding site of ribose moiety of NAD^+ in *CboFDH* (PDB: 5DN9). (D) Binding site of formate in *TcFDH* (PDB: 6T8Z). Polar and π - π interactions are displayed in yellow and orange, respectively. Structures were depicted using PyMol.^[10]

Intriguingly, *PsFDH* features π -stacking between His224 and His380 (Figure 3A), which is absent in *GraFDH* as the corresponding position to His380 does not comprise of a His but a Lys (Lys379 in *GraFDH*). This might be an additional factor befitting the structural adjustment. Further comparison with *CboFDH* reveals that all positions are differing (Figure 5C). This suggests that positions Arg223 and His224 are not directly involved in determining the cofactor specificity. However, in combination with substitution of Asp222, it apparently boosts the activity towards NADP^+ due to the basic properties of both residues, which engage in polar interactions with the phosphate group as present in *GraFDH* (Figure 5B). This is evidenced by the kinetic parameters observed in *CboFDH* mutants Asp195Gln and Asp195Gln/Tyr196Arg/Gln197Asn. While the single mutant exhibits less favorable kinetics, the triple mutant demonstrates significantly improved kinetic values, highlighting the importance of these interactions.^[48,49]

Besides NAD(P)^+ , almost all structures contain azide as a formate analog. However, due to its linear structure, it does not entirely mimic formate. Crystal structures with formate are challenging to achieve as the reaction rapidly takes place, hampering clean crystal formation. However, with a rapid cryocooling at lower pH, Yilmazer *et al.*^[22] managed to crystallize FDH from *Thermoanaerobacterium thermophilum* DSM 1495 (*TcFDH*) with NAD^+ and formate, revealing the precise orientation of the formate in the active site (Figure 5D). Formate is precisely positioned within the active site through polar interactions involving Ile94, Asn120, Arg259 and His311 for the upcoming hydride transfer. Phe70 is likely limiting the size of the active site and restricting binding conformations of formate.

Furthermore, the critical role of some conserved residues was reported. Tyr102 in *PsFDH* (Tyr73 in *CboFDH*) is essential for stabilization of the closed conformation as mutation to Phe resulted in 80-fold increased K_M value. Moreover, crystallization of the Tyr102Phe mutant in apo-form showed that the mutation did not crucially affect the overall fold. However, the absence of the interdomain hydrogen bond between Tyr102 and Gln313 (Gln287 in *CboFDH*) is hypothesized to destabilize the closed conformation.^[50] These residues are highly conserved among all reported FDHs. Arg174 was identified as an essential residue for cofactor binding in *CboFDH* utilizing adenosine 5'-O-[S-(4-hydroxy-2,3-dioxobutyl)]-thiophosphate (AMPS-HDB).^[51] This NAD⁺ analog contains a dicarbonyl group at the position where normally the pyrophosphate is located. The dicarbonyl group reacts with Arg residues and allows the identification of relevant Arg residues for activity and stability. Arg174 is involved in the binding of the pyrophosphate group of NAD⁺ and crucial for activity as substitution with Gln resulted in drastic loss of activity.^[51]

4. Classification of Structural Features into the Phylogenetic Context

Structural information can be often viewed in a phylogenetic context to gain more insight. Thus, relevant positions with their reported affiliations were analyzed using the A2CA tool.^[52,53]

Figure 6 visualizes the correlation between residue positions and the phylogenetic origin. The common NAD(P)-binding motif G(A)XGXXG is present in all FDHs. Among the reported FDHs, nearly all positions are conserved including the Arg174 residue which was reported to be involved in binding of the pyrophosphate of the NAD⁺.^[51] Due to its high degree of conservation, it likely takes the same role in all reported FDHs.

The residues located on the loop, responsible for cofactor specificity, show some variety among the phylogenetic groups. For instance, fungal FDHs mostly contain Asp, Tyr and Gln, whereas in plant FDHs Asp and Arg are always set with the last position being more variable. Bacterial FDHs contain predominantly Asp, Arg and His, with two exceptions: The first are *SaFDH* and *BsFDH* due to their rather distant relation to the remaining bacterial FDHs and the second are the NADP⁺-accepting ones. In the latter, the Asp residue is absent and always substituted to smaller or less acidic residue. The exceptional role of the Asp residue for cofactor specificity was already discussed in previous studies.^[15,28] Furthermore, the following residues Arg196 and His197 proved to be advantageous for NADP⁺-acceptance, as *GraFDH* was showing decent kinetic parameters with this combination, whereas single substitution of the Asp residue in *CboFDH*, resulting in Gln, Tyr and Gln did not yield comparable values.^[48] Interestingly, Arg and His are also present in most NAD⁺-dependent bacterial FDHs, producing a rather basic surrounding for the neutral ribose moiety. Moreover, the reported His-His π -stacking between position 197 and 356 (both corresponding to the positions of *CboFDH* in the alignment) is consistent with all FDHs sharing the Asp, Arg and

Figure 6. Minimum evolution tree of reported FDHs (compare with Figure 2; but here were only biochemically characterized representatives included) and alignment of selected residues referenced to the *CboFDH* sequence. Aligned residue positions are clustered by their function. Naturally NADP⁺ accepting FDHs are highlighted by the red box. Figure was created with the aid of the A2CA tool.^[52,53]

His residues. This π -stacking is not present in the NADP⁺-accepting FDHs due to the absence of the His356 residue. This further underlines the importance of these features as it was previously observed to counteract the loop shift, occurring in NADP⁺-accepting FDHs to accommodate the phosphate group.^[15] Probably, the NAD⁺-dependent bacterial FDHs evolved from a NADP⁺-accepting ancestor as they contain more residues (Arg and His) which have more potential to be beneficial for NADP⁺- than NAD⁺-acceptance.

The formate and the nicotinamide binding sites are highly conserved among all representatives except for position 93, which is either Val or Ile. Due to the fact that this residue interacts solely with its backbone, this slight deviation can be neglected. Overall, this suggests that there is little to no variation regarding the catalytic site, including orientation of the nicotinamide, and hydride donor. Likely, all FDHs are binding formate in the same orientation as predicted for the *CboFDH* and reported for *TcFDH* from *Thermochaetoides thermophila* DSM 1495.^[22,54] Positions Tyr73 and Gln 287 are also highly conserved. This underlines their importance for the reported stabilization of the closed conformation, which seems to be equally important for all FDHs.

5. Reported Reactions

Initially FDHs were expected to have a very narrow substrate scope as the formate binding site was highly conserved, meaning that likely no other substrates are utilized in the native environment. However, FDHs were observed to have a wider substrate spectrum than anticipated. Activities with formate esters and formamides, as well as the back reaction consuming CO₂ and NADH to form formate and NAD⁺ were observed.

5.1. Formate Oxidation

Oxidation of formate is mediated by direct hydride transfer from formate to the NAD(P)⁺ cofactor without any other involvement of residues or other cofactors. This requires sufficient proximity of the formate hydrogen to the C4 carbon of the nicotinamide moiety of the NAD(P)⁺ cosubstrate (Scheme 2).^[42]

Upon binding and transition into the closed conformation, the oxygen of the Ile backbone exerts a repelling force on the formate hydrogen, promoting the proximity and thus the hydride transfer. Gaseous CO₂ escapes and continuously shifts the equilibrium towards formate oxidation, making the reaction extremely efficient. As no other cofactors or metals are involved, the hydride transfer reaction relies solely on the proximity of donor and recipient. Therefore, a fine-tuned mechanism is necessary to efficiently catalyze this reaction. This is underlined by the highly conserved catalytic site and residues involved in closed conformation stabilization (Figure 4). Likely, the dynamic properties of FDHs are one of the driving forces of the reaction.

5.2. CO₂ Reduction

Initially, FDHs were considered to perform formate oxidation irreversibly. However, recent reports suggested that CO₂ reduction is within the realms of possibility, though with much less efficiency due to the redox potential of −420 mV favoring

Scheme 2. Reaction mechanism of formate oxidation (adapted from Gou *et al.*^[42]).

Scheme 3. Proposed HCO₃[−] reduction mechanism of FDHs (adapted from Aslan *et al.*^[55]).

formate oxidation.^[9] Thus, driven by the globally rising CO₂ levels, formate dehydrogenases gained more importance due to their CO₂-fixing potential. Based on current knowledge, reaction mechanism involves HCO₃[−] as hydride acceptor. After hydride transfer, the intermediate rearranges into formate by eliminating hydroxide (Scheme 3).^[55]

Despite intensive studies on various FDHs, the molecular details of the mechanism especially of CO₂ reduction, are still not fully uncovered and only little success rates were reported from screening of hundred-thousands of mutants for enzyme optimization. For instance, activities in the range of 6 to 10 U mg^{−1} for formate oxidation have been achieved, whilst activities in the range of only 3 to 35 mU mg^{−1} were observed for CO₂ reduction.^[21,55] Therefore, further improvement by directed evolution and AI guidance are necessary to fully unlock the potential of FDHs.

5.3. Oxidation of Formate Derivatives

Formate esters such as methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl, phenyl and phenethyl formate as well as 1-acetoxy-4-formoxy butane were identified as suitable substrates for FDHs.^[56,57] As a result, FDHs perform oxidative ester cleavage yielding besides CO₂ the respective alcohol. The postulated reaction mechanism has parallels with formate oxidation such as the initial hydride transfer (Scheme 4A). However, this yields a carbocation for formate esters, which is believed to be relocated the positive charge to the ester oxygen, which is subsequently attacked by H₂O to form the carbonic acid monoester. Due to the instability of the latter, CO₂ is eliminated giving the respective alcohol (Scheme 5).

Recently, Maier *et al.*^[54] demonstrated that formamides, including formamide, *N*-methylformamide and *N,N*-dimethylformamide can be converted by FDHs as well. The reaction mechanism is hypothesized to follow a similar pattern as the oxidative formate ester cleavage (Scheme 4B). Instead of the carbonic acid monoester, carbamic acid is formed as an intermediate and rapidly decomposes into CO₂ and the respective amine. However, the analytical proof, for instance, the confirmation of the carbamic acid intermediate, which should be detectable in trace amounts, is still pending.

Both reactions are most likely irreversible, as according to the mechanism, formation of the carbonic acid monoester or the carbamic acid with subsequent H₂O elimination would be

Scheme 4. Postulated reaction mechanisms for oxidative cleavage of (A) formate esters and (B) formamides.^[54,57]

Scheme 5. Different utilizations of FDHs. (A) NADPH regeneration and FDH-mediated ester cleavage of phenethylformate to yield 2-phenylethanol (adapted from Vorster *et al.*^[56]). (B) NADH regeneration by formate ester cleavage of octyl formate by FDH in a biphasic system. Organic phase serves as substrate reservoir and product sink (adapted from Churakova *et al.*^[102]). (C) FDH catalyzed oxidative cleavage of *N*-methylformamide for NADPH regeneration and methylamine supply for reductive amination (adapted from Maier *et al.*^[54]).

required to form the carbocation, which then would serve as electron acceptor. Therefore, it is highly questionable, if this thermodynamically extremely unfavorable process can be mediated by the FDHs.

6. Engineering of FDHs

Due to the utility and potential of FDHs for various bioprocesses, FDHs became a prominent target for enzyme engineering. Especially, alteration of the substrate specificity and increase of stability were attempted by either directed evolution or rational design (Table 2). The well-characterized *Cbo*FDH was frequently used as for enzyme engineering,

though other FDHs from fungi, bacteria and plant were also targeted (Table 2).

6.1. Stability

FDHs were already shown to have remarkable stability in presence of various solvents such as methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, and DMF among others and have exhibited decent thermal stability with melting temperatures up to 63 °C.^[15,54,72] Nevertheless, many attempts were made to further improve various representatives.

The first stability improvements of *Cbo*FDH focused on the cysteine residues as they are susceptible to oxidation. Therefore, it was attempted to substitute the Cys residues, with the C23S and C23S/C262A variants being the ones with beneficial properties.^[14] The latter was found to be more stable towards mechanical stress and at air-water interfaces, though the sensitivity towards salts increased.^[73] Another approach was to incorporate a disulfide bond and by this, utilize the Cys23 position. Based on the structural data position, Ala10 was identified to be in proximity and substituted to Cys- allowing disulfide formation between Cys10 and Cys23 and improving the melting temperature and k_{cat} values of the *Cbo*FDH.^[58] Along the line, methionine residues, which are also prone to oxidation, were elucidated in *Gh*FDH. Met residues putatively located on the surface were substituted with Leu, resulting in a distinctly more chemically stable variant M225L/M234L/M243L. This variant showed remarkable tolerance towards H₂O₂ with a 2-fold lower inactivation constant. However, this mutation did not improve thermal stability.^[62]

Bulut *et al.*^[59] investigated the role of conserved residues Phe285, Gln287 and His311 on the stability and pH optimum of *Cbo*FDH. The mutants Phe285Thr/His311Gln and His311Gln were the most efficient in terms of thermal stability with melting temperatures of 73 °C and 77°, respectively. This was significantly higher than the melting temperature of 64 °C determined for the wild type. However, the more stable variants showed drastically reduced activity. The role of these residues on activity and among others, was shown to be detrimental in previous studies.^[60]

Carter *et al.*^[61] demonstrated that mutations N187S and T321S incorporated in *Cbo*FDH increase the activity and stability in ionic liquids with up to 40% (v/v) of 1,3-dimethylimidazolium dimethylphosphate ([MMIm][Me₂PO₄]). The double mutant showed 5-fold higher activity than the wild type. Fluorescence spectroscopy measurements revealed that the wild type undergoes significant structural changes at 50% [MMIm][Me₂PO₄], whereas the N187S single mutant and the N187S/T321S double mutant did not. Therefore, it was hypothesized that the N187S mutation is responsible for the observed improvements. Interestingly, both mutations did not significantly affect the thermal stability, indicating that chemical and thermal stability consist of various aspects.

Table 2. Reported engineered FDHs with changed properties.			
FDH	Mutation	Effect	Reference
Stability Variants			
<i>Cbo</i> FDH	C23S	Increased stability	[14]
	A10C	Increased stability	[58]
	H311Q	Increased thermal stability Shift of pH optimum Drastically reduced activity	[59, 60]
	F285T/H311Q	Increased thermal stability Drastically reduced activity	[59]
	187S/T321S	Increased activity and stability in presence of ionic liquids	[61]
<i>Gh</i> FDH	M225L/M234L/M243L	Increase chemical stability	[62]
Altered substrate specificity and activity Variants			
<i>Cbo</i> FDH	D195Q/Y196H	Acceptance of NADP ⁺ Bispecific for NAD ⁺ and NADP ⁺	[48]
	D195Q/Y196R/Q197N	Acceptance of NADP ⁺	[49]
	D195A	Acceptance of 3'-NADP ⁺	[63]
	D195G	Acceptance of 3'-NADP ⁺	[63]
	D195G/Y196S	Improved specificity for 3'-NADP ⁺ Distinctly lower overall activity	[63]
	C23S/T130I	Increased catalytic efficiency with NAD ⁺	[54]
<i>Cm</i> FDH	D195S/Y196A	Increased catalytic efficiency towards NAD ⁺	[64]
<i>Kp</i> FDH	D195Q/Y196R/Q197H	Acceptance of NADP ⁺	[19]
<i>Cd</i> FDH	D197Q/Y198R/Q199N/A372S/K371T/ ΔQ375/K167R/H16L/K159R	Acceptance of NADP ⁺ and increased catalytic efficiency	[21]
<i>Tc</i> FDH	G93H/I94Y	Increased catalytic efficiency for HCO ₃ ⁻ reduction	[65]
	N120C	Loss of activity with formate Retained activity with HCO ₃ ⁻	[66]
<i>Pc</i> FDH	E141N/Q313E	Enabling of glyoxylate reduction	[67]
<i>Ps</i> FDH	A198G/D221Q/C255A/H379K/S380V	Specificity towards NADP ⁺ Improved catalytic efficiency for NADP ⁺ Improved affinity for formate	[68]
<i>Bst</i> FDH	G146M/A287G	Decreased K _M for NADP ⁺ Increased catalytic efficiency	[69]
	I124V/G146H/A287G	Decreased K _M for formate Increased catalytic efficiency	[69]
Mixed Variants			
<i>Cbo</i> FDH	V328I/F285W	Increased conversion of CO ₂ Increased thermal stability Increased affinity for formate	[70]
	V324G/F285W	Increased conversion of CO ₂ Increased thermal stability Increased affinity for formate	[70]
<i>Ap</i> FDH	D222Q/A199G/H380S/C256A/C146S	Acceptance of NADP ⁺ Increased activity Increased stability	[30]
<i>Myc</i> FDH	C145S/D221Q/C255V	Acceptance of NADP ⁺ Increased activity with NAD ⁺ and NADP ⁺ Bispecific for NAD ⁺ and NADP ⁺	[71]
	C145S/A198G/D221Q/C255V	Acceptance of NADP ⁺ Improved catalytic efficiency for NADP ⁺ Increased stability towards α-haloketones	[71]
<i>Gm</i> FDH	F290D	Increased catalytic efficiency for NAD ⁺ Increased thermal stability	[72]

[Correction added on 20 September 2024, after first online publication: Reference column was updated in this version.]

6.2. Alteration of Substrate Specificity and Improving of Activity

Due to the increasing demand for NADPH regeneration systems, many approaches were made to shift the cofactor specificity of FDHs towards NADP⁺. The Asp residue (Asp195 in *CboFDH*) was already identified to be essential for the clear preference of FDHs for NAD⁺. Therefore, this Asp position and the downstream located residues Y196 and Q197, which are part of the cofactor binding loop, were targeted in various mutagenesis studies (Table 2). For *CboFDH*, the triple mutation D195Q/Y196R/Q197N proved to be the most efficient and was later on also utilized in *KpFDH* and *CdFDH*.^[19,21] The latter was further improved through multiple rounds of site saturation mutagenesis targeting various positions in proximity of the cofactor. This resulted in the final *CdFDH* variant D197Q/Y198R/Q199 N/A372S/K371T/ΔQ375/K167R/H16L/K159R, with an activity of 3.2 U/mg towards NADP⁺. This variant distinctly outperformed the initial triple mutant, which showed activity of merely 0.5 U/mg. In molecular dynamics simulations, a general increase of correlated and anticorrelated motions in the final variant compared to the wild type was observed.^[21] This indicates higher flexibility of multiple segments probably befitting activity. However, no information on stability was provided.

Besides NADPH, non-canonical cofactor analogs are likewise of interest, as they would enable to decouple the enzymatic reactions from the existing metabolism *in vivo*. One these cofactor analogs is 3'-NADPH. 3'-NADPH differs from NADPH in the position of the phosphate, which is located at the 3'-position of the ribose instead of the 2'-position as it is in NADPH. It was initially described as non-natural inhibitor of NADPH-dependent enzymes, but was later on discovered to occur naturally as metabolite produced by the plant pathogen *Xanthomonas oryzae*.^[74] To utilize 3'-NADPH, Vainstein *et al.*^[63] engineered *CboFDH* to accept 3'-NADP⁺. Site-saturation mutagenesis of the already described loop responsible for cofactor specificity resulted in the single mutants D195 A and D195G, with specific rates for 3'-NADP⁺ of around 0.2 and 0.15 s⁻¹, respectively. The wild type did not display detectable activity with the analogous cosubstrate. Further round of mutagenesis yielded the double mutant D195G/Y196S showing the highest specificity for 3'-NADP⁺, although the overall activity was three orders of magnitude lower. Furthermore, the specificity increased primarily due to the distinctly lower activity with NAD⁺ compared to 3'-NADP⁺.

One remarkable achievement in regard of CO₂ utilization was the *TcFDH* N120C variant. Here, the single substitution resulted in complete abortion of formate oxidation activity whilst HCO₃⁻ reduction ability was retained.^[66] The removal of the highly conserved and polar Asn residue, which is normally involved in formate binding, likely gives an unfavorable orientation of the formate. This seems to be not the case for the HCO₃⁻. Interestingly, the same substitution in *CmFDH* eliminated activity with formate and HCO₃⁻, indicating that despite the high degree of conservation among FDHs, the individual representatives display unique properties, especially

in regard of the reverse reduction reaction.^[66] This would drive the equilibrium further to the reduction side as the oxidation is abolished. However, in later attempts to engineer the *TcFDH*, Çakar *et al.*^[65] targeted various positions for site-saturation mutagenesis, including Asn120, which in particular did not yield any hits in the screening. Nevertheless, mutations G93H/I94Y were identified to increase the catalytic efficiency 5-fold towards HCO₃⁻ compared to the wild type. Counterintuitively, incorporation of bulkier residues might result in a wider active site pocket to accommodate the bigger HCO₃⁻ as suggested by molecular dynamics simulations. Additionally, the His93 might form polar interactions with the HCO₃⁻ to further stabilize the correct orientation, needed for efficient hydride transfer.

Shinoda *et al.*^[67] demonstrated the transformation of *PcFDH* to a glyoxylate reductase by substitution of two residues. Mutations E141 N/Q313E increased the catalytic efficiency for glyoxylate reduction by 20,000-fold compared to the wild type and simultaneously nearly completely prevented formate oxidation. This reveals the potential within FDHs and how versatile enzyme engineering can be applied.

6.3. Dual Impact Variants

Some mutations have wide-ranging effects on FDHs. For instance, *MycFDH* seems to dually benefit from C145S/C255V mutations as they not only increased chemical stability towards α-haloketons but also improved catalytic efficiency with NAD⁺ and NADP⁺. These positions are close to the formate and cosubstrate binding regions but not directly involved in interactions with either one, suggesting some indirect effects.^[71]

As stated above the FDH catalyzed reduction of CO₂ to formate was yet extremely unfavorable resulting in only low activities in the μMg⁻¹ range. Thus, engineering was performed to increase the respective reaction rate. *CboFDH* mutants V328I/F285W and V354G/F285W showed not only increased catalytic efficiency for HCO₃⁻ of 0.0042 and 0.0041 mM⁻¹s⁻¹, respectively, but also increased their thermal stability. MDS analysis revealed lower RMSD values over the simulation duration, indicating that the mutant variants exhibit a higher degree of rigidity, likely responsible for the increased stability. Moreover, docking experiments suggested that HCO₃⁻ forms more polar interactions within the active site of the mutants, befitting the conversion. Remarkably, these mutations distinctly reduced the *K_M* value for formate down to 0.81 mM.^[70] It is important to note that the improvement of the catalytic efficiency is primarily caused by the increased affinity towards HCO₃⁻, whereas the maximal activity was not significantly affected by the mutations. This is likely connected to the improved affinity towards formate and needs to be further elucidated.

Wild type *AspFDH* features one of the highest activities with NAD⁺ among metal-independent FDHs reported so far, making it an attractive target for enzyme engineering. Multiple rounds of directed evolution yielded the quintuple mutant *AspFDH* D222Q/A199G/H380S/C256A/C146S, with shifted specificity towards NADP⁺, increased activity and stability. Specificity shift

was mediated by D222Q as reported for other FDHs.^[48,71] 199 G/H380S contributed to further activity improvements and C256A/C146S had an stabilizing effect.^[30] This variant features one of the highest activities reported with NADP⁺ as cosubstrate and elevates the potential of enzyme engineering.

6.4. Reaction Engineering

Besides enzyme engineering, other options such as reaction engineering were explored. The usage of osmolytes proved to be an interesting approach to boost not only activity but also stability. For instance, Gajardo-Parra *et al.*^[76] elucidated the impact of the osmolytes trimethylamine *N*-oxide (TMAO), betaine, glycerol, and trehalose on the performance of *Cbo*FDH. They showed that the presence of TMAO increases the activity of *Cbo*FDH by 12% compared to the buffer control but does not affect the long-term activity as the activity decline over time was comparable to the control. Interestingly, usage of betaine resulted in 80% retained activity after 10 days, which was a 3-fold improvement compared to TMAO and the buffer control. All osmolytes also increased the melting temperature compared to the buffer control (61 °C), with trehalose resulting in the highest increase of 3 °C. Molecular dynamics simulations suggest that the tested osmolytes affect the solvation layers of FDH in different ways. According to the authors, TMAO and betaine increase the water density at the surface of *Cbo*FDH, explaining the elevated activity, whereas glycerol and trehalose exclude water from the surface, resulting in higher thermal stability.

An additional aspect rarely considered is pressure. Studies have shown that at an elevated temperature of 45 °C and pressure up to the kbar range, the *Cbo*FDH displays an increase of catalytic efficiency by one order of magnitude. This improvement was primarily due to the increased affinity towards formate, caused by the increased pressure, whereas the k_{cat} value remained unaffected. Interestingly, the K_{M} value of NAD⁺ was not affected.^[77] Addition of the osmolyte TMAO and its mixtures with the macromolecular crowding agent dextran further doubled the catalytic efficiency. At pressures above 1 kbar, a decrease in performance was observed, likely attributed to small structural changes as revealed by FTIR measurements.^[77] This demonstrates the various effects of different additives and pressures on FDH performance, adding another layer to the complexity of FDH biocatalysis.

7. Application of FDHs

In different industries, most chemicals are either isolated from natural sources or synthesized *via* chemical routes. However, these options can be inefficient and costly and chemical routes often use petrochemical agents and can lead to unwanted side products. Biotechnology can provide an alternative to introduce novel or replace existing production routes. Lately, FDHs were applied in various bioprocesses (Table 3). Here, the focus will be on recent applications.

Primarily, FDHs are used as a cofactor regeneration system as demonstrated for production of cinnamyl cinnamate, a high-value aromatic compound used in fragrances and flavors. In this process, FDH can be applied for *in situ* cofactor regeneration to supply NADH for the alcohol dehydrogenase that catalyzes the reduction of cinnamaldehyde to cinnamyl alcohol. The latter is subsequently coupled with cinnamic acid by esterification catalyzed by a lipase to yield the cinnamyl cinnamate.^[95] Another possibility demonstrated for flavors and fragrances was the production (*R*)-1-phenylethanol. This involved the ene-reductase (OYE) YgjM, reducing O₂ to H₂O₂ and FDH as the NADH regeneration system. The formed H₂O₂ was used by *rAae*UPO to produce (*R*)-1-phenylethanol from ethylbenzene.^[96]

The use of FDHs to fuel enzymes that can lead to enantiopure products of amino acids, α -hydroxy acids, and ketones have also been reported.^[97–99] L-Amino acids are in general inexpensive while D-amino acids are scarce in nature.^[100] Therefore, L-amino acid as a substrate is quite favorable for industrial application. An *in vivo* cascade was previously demonstrated in *E. coli* where L-amino acids were converted to D-amino acids in an enzymatic system comprising of L-amino acid deaminase, diamino acid dehydrogenase, and a formate dehydrogenase from *Burkholderia stabilis*.^[98] The production of enantiopure (*R*) or (*S*)- α -hydroxy acids from L-amino acids was also done with FDH fueling the regeneration of NAD⁺ for 2-hydroxyisocaproate dehydrogenase.^[97] It was reported that the designed cascade can transform up to 200 mM of the substrate. Meanwhile, Chen *et al.*^[99] showed the possibility to produce (*R*)-aminated ketones with 99% *ee* from a trienzymatic cascade containing ω -transaminase, an amine dehydrogenase, and a formate dehydrogenase using ammonium formate as the sacrificial substrate. These chiral amines are important drug precursors and active pharmaceutical ingredients, and the trienzymatic cascade enabled the production of these (*R*)-chiral amines. Additional routes to produce the sugar L-ribulose and the herbicide L-phosphinothricin were also shown recently with FDH being the regeneration system.^[101]

FDHs can not only be used as sole cofactor regeneration systems, but also be utilized in different ways as shown for the production of 2-phenylethanol (2-PE), an important chemical in flavors and fragrances as it produces a rose-like aroma. Vorster *et al.*^[56] demonstrated the production of 2-PE through the selective oxygenation of cinnamaldehyde to hydrocinnamaldehyde by an OYE. From this study, the reaction was then coupled with a Baeyer-Villiger monoxygenase (BVMO) which produces the corresponding formate esters from hydrocinnamaldehyde that can spontaneously hydrolyze to 2-PE. As both OYE and BVMO require NADPH as a co-substrate, FDH variants from *Candida boidinii* were used to regenerate NADPH. Remarkably in this case, FDH was fulfilling a double function—cofactor regeneration and oxidative cleavage of the phenethyl formate yielding the 2-PE. Particularly in this setup, FDH was the ideal regeneration system as it additionally provides detoxification of formate, which is formed by the hydrolysis of phenethyl formate. This is mediated either by conversion of the accumulating formate or prevention of its formation due to the FDH catalyzed oxidative cleavage of the phenethyl formate.^[56] The

Table 3. Application of FDHs in cascade setups and as fusion proteins.

FDH	Partner protein	Purpose	Reference
Cascade Setup			
CboFDH	Alcohol dehydrogenase from <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	Detoxification of acetaldehyde accumulating during aldol condensation between <i>p</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde and L-threonine catalyzed by L-threonine transaldolase	[78]
CboFDH (A10C)	Leucine dehydrogenase was from <i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Chiral purification of L-norvaline and L-phenylglycine from racemic mixture	[79]
MycFDH	D-Lactate dehydrogenase from <i>Pediococcus acidilactici</i>	Production of salivianic acid A	[80]
CboFDH	Cytochrome P450 monooxygenase 153A7 from <i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. HXN-200	Hydroxylation of (–)-limonene to (–)-perillyl alcohol intermediate; further conversion into perillamine	[81]
CboFDH	Chimeric styrene monooxygenase (Fus-SMO)	Epoxidation of styrene to styrene oxide intermediate; further conversion into 2-phenylglycinol or phenylethanolamine	[82]
CboFDH (C235/D195Q/Y196R/Q197N)	Reductive aminase from <i>Aspergillus oryzae</i>	Production of <i>N</i> -methylcyclohexylamine	[54]
CboFDH (D195Q/Y196R/Q197N)	Ene-reductase from <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> and Baeyer-Villiger monooxygenase from <i>Aspergillus oryzae</i>	Production of 2-phenolethanol	[56]
OpFDH	Ribitol dehydrogenase from <i>Providencia alcalifaciens</i> RIMD 1656011	Production of allitol	[83]
CboFDH	Xylose reductase from <i>Candida tenuis</i> CBS 4435	Production of xylitol	[84]
BstFDH	LM15 phenylacetone monooxygenase mutant (KYP10950)	Whole-cell process to produce esomeprazole	[85]
Fusion proteins			
MycFDH	3-Ketoacyl-facyl-carrier-protein-reductase (KR) from <i>Synechococcus</i> PCC 7942	Production of ethyl-(S)-3-hydroxy-3-phenylpropanoate	[86]
CboFDH	Phenyl dehydrogenase from <i>Bacillus halodurans</i> .	Production of L-phenylalanine	[87]
CboFDH	Leucine dehydrogenase from <i>Bacillus cereus</i> ATCC 10987	Production of L-tert leucine	[88]
CboFDH	D-Lactate dehydrogenase (D-LDH ^{NSM}) from <i>Lactobacillus pentosus</i> .	Production of (R)-3-phenyllactic acid	[89]
CboFDH	P450 BM3 from <i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	Conversion of different substrates	[90]
CboFDH	Glutamate dehydrogenase from <i>Clostridium symbiosum</i>	Continuous removal of ammonia for reductive amination of α -ketoglutarate	[91]
CboFDH	Alanine dehydrogenase from <i>Halomonas elongata</i>	Amino donor to transaminases for production of vanillyl amine	[92]
CboFDH	Azoreductase from <i>Rhodococcus opacus</i> 1CP	Reduction of azo dyes	[93]
CboFDH	Chimeric amine dehydrogenase (cFL1-AmbDH)	Reduction of 5-methyl-2-hexanone to 5-methyl-hexyl-2-(R)-amine	[94]

formate ester cleavage ability of FDHs can also be utilized in different setups. The work of Churakova *et al.*^[102] showed the possibility of using the formic acid ester, octyl formate, to make a biphasic system that can serve as a substrate reservoir and a product sink. It was shown that FDH can mediate oxidative hydrolysis of octyl formate to regenerate NADH for 2-hydroxybiphenyl-3-monooxygenase (HbpA). However, the main limitations comprising of sluggish phase transfer of the substrates and potentially O₂ restriction have to be addressed for reliable future approaches.^[102] Another example of a dual role in application was shown by Maier *et al.*^[54] who reported FDH catalyzed formamide cleavage for the first time. This ability was employed to fuel the reductive amination of cyclohexanone to *N*-methylcyclohexamine catalyzed by the imine-reductase from *Aspergillus oryzae*. This reaction requires besides the cyclohexanone additionally methylamine and NADPH, both provided by the FDH through oxidative cleavage of *N*-methylformamide. In a whole cell approach, conversion rates of up to 72% could be achieved with *N*-methylformamide as the sole hydride donor.^[54]

Besides bioprocesses, FDHs were utilized for quantification of NAD⁺ in biological samples. Compared to alternative methods, the fluorometric assay involving FDH does not require chromatographic separation and is straightforward to use. Additionally, FDHs high selectivity for NAD⁺ proves to be useful. Quantification of NAD⁺ levels was successfully demonstrated for rat brain tissue and mitochondria employing FDH from *Ogataea parapolymorpha*.^[103]

The production of proteins can be an arduous task. The generation of fusion proteins from compatible systems has sparked interests to put two genes in one open-reading frame. Moreover, they can offer various advantages including improved stability, increased production levels, improved catalytic efficiency and avoidance of the accumulation of the potentially unstable intermediate. The latter are primarily mediated by the substrate channeling effect, where the intermediate is nearly directly transferred to the next active site due to their proximity.^[104] Although activities from fusion protein may differ from the parental enzyme, several researchers have already delved on constructing bifunctional biocatalysts together with FDHs (Table 3). Interestingly, fusion proteins can feature deviating substrate specificities as shown for instance by Ngo *et al.*^[93], where the azoreductase-FDH fusion protein was able to convert bulkier substrates more efficiently than the unfused azoreductase.

8. Summary and Outlook

The last years, biocatalysis experienced a huge leap forward that can be also seen in the developments made in the domain of formate dehydrogenases. An astonishing amount of new FDHs and structural data were reported and collected increasing the mechanistical understanding. Moreover, the role of various residues in different FDHs was unveiled—solidifying the basis for enzyme engineering. This led to variety of new insights on how to modify FDHs, as variants were created with improved

thermal and/or chemical stability and shifted cosubstrate preference, perfectly fitting the intended purpose. Additionally, reaction engineering approaches such as the addition of osmolytes and increase of pressure could also be beneficial for FDH performance. This knowledge could be of interest for many other reactions. Overall, this resulted in the discovery of the most stable and most efficient oxygen-tolerant FDHs so far.

Furthermore, despite being known for many decades, the substrate specificity, particularly on the hydride donor site, was finally explored—revealing a distinctly wider range than previously expected. More importantly, the acceptance of formate esters and formamides as hydride donor should be mentioned here. As this knowledge was acquired just recently, not much alteration by enzyme engineering was possible yet, leaving room for further improvement.

Many NAD(P)H-dependent bioprocesses were reported to be reliant on FDHs giving satisfactory yields displaying the competitive capacity of this regeneration system towards the alternatives. Nevertheless, FDHs were not only utilized as a plain cofactor regeneration system but fulfilled dual functions with direct contribution towards substrate conversion, such as the oxidative cleavage of phenethyl formate to 2-phenylethanol. Various examples show that application of FDHs is not limited to sole cofactor regeneration, further underlining the potential of FDHs.

With the recently growing global climate crisis, FDHs emerged as one potential candidate for CO₂-fixation. Even though progress was made in this regard such as creation of variants with improved catalytic efficiency and activity, the application of these processes has still multiple hurdles to overcome. For instance, the activity remains in the mU mg⁻¹ range, which is too low and the electron donor NAD(P)H is way too costly for sustainable application. Thus, further improvement will be necessary to unleash the potential that lies within the FDHs.

With the new, especially bioinformatical methods (e.g. AlphaFold3) and other AI-based tools even more advancement is to be expected, forecasting a bright future for FDHs and their potential applications.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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